

OPERAS-P

OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN THE
EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA FOR SSH - PREPARATION

WP7: Communication, Outreach and Advocacy

Advocacy Guide

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Deliverable 7.3
Advocacy Guide

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I. Introduction

A. About the OPERAS Advocacy Special Interest Group

This Deliverable has been prepared by the OPERAS (Open Access in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities) Special Interest Group on Advocacy for Open Access Publishing in the Social Sciences and Humanities (Advocacy SIG) as part of T7.4 of the project [OPERAS-P](#) (Preparing open access in the European research area through scholarly communication). The project's primary goal is to support the development of OPERAS. It thus follows three objectives: to support the ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) application, start the implementation of innovative services and support the expansion of the consortium to improve the scholarly ecosystem in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). It furthermore ensures the sustainable outreach and advocacy for open scholarly communication in the SSH.

The Advocacy SIG currently has eight member organizations: Göttingen University Library (SUB Göttingen), Institute for Computational Linguistics "A. Zampolli" (CNR-ILC), Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IBL PAN), Max Weber Stiftung (MWS), National Documentation Centre (EKT), OpenEdition, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, University of Turin (UniTo), University of Zadar (UNIZD). It is coordinated by Max Weber Stiftung. Organizations interested in contributing to the SIG can contact Elisabeth Ernst (ernst@maxweberstiftung.de). The SIG is open to any member of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, specifically including "observers" wishing to participate in the SIG.¹

The Advocacy SIG has produced a White Paper on advocacy for Open Access publishing in July 2018.² The White Paper addresses the importance of Open Science for the SSH, highlighting the role of a distributed research infrastructure like OPERAS in advocating for Open Access publishing models. Furthermore, the paper discusses the importance of the SSH in Open Science, showing how Open Science itself benefits from considering and accommodating the needs of researchers from different disciplinary backgrounds. While OPERAS does not endorse a specific Open Access publishing model, the infrastructure partners advocate for publication processes that can meet the present demand for Open Access, transparency, and open source tools in scholarly communication.

This Deliverable uses the results of the White Paper to present some updates and to involve the OPERAS community in the ongoing task of advocating for the SSH and Open Science. It therefore focuses on the preparation of workshops and other forms of events to receive feedback from the community. The Advocacy SIG will make the results of the events public and use these to come up with recommendations for OPERAS members on

¹ To find out more about the different types of membership and how to join a SIG: <https://www.operas.unito.it/about/want-to-know-more/want-to-join-operas/>.

² see: Elisabeth Heinemann, Andrea Bertino, Francesca Di Donato, Aysa Ekanger, Elena Giglia, Barbara Jędraszko, Michael Kaiser, Lisa Matthias, Alessia Smaniotta. (2018, July 30). OPERAS Advocacy White Paper. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1324036>.

specific advocacy actions and projects. The ultimate goal of the next OPERAS Advocacy White Paper is to formulate concrete ideas for actions and projects that OPERAS members and other relevant stakeholders can carry out or plan to adopt within their organizations.

This document is intended for all stakeholders actively involved in Open Access in the SSH, particularly for members of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure. This includes publishers, publication platforms, libraries, and infrastructure providers. While the 2018 White Paper has ultimately focused on advocacy targeting researchers at different career stages, this Deliverable widens the scope to include policy- and decision-makers, both at a national and European level.

The Deliverable starts by defining Open Science and Open Access, as well as Advocacy, and presenting the SIG's main target groups and stakeholders. It then presents the SIG's idea for a guide for addressing researchers' needs related to Open Access publishing. This guide will be a direct continuation of the 2018 White Paper and will be based on the results of a survey, as well as the results of the three planned Advocacy Workshops. The Deliverable then outlines the topic of advocacy for the SSH, presenting first results of a panel discussion. The SIG has agreed on a third topic, national channels for Open Access publishing, which will be further detailed together with the OPERAS national nodes. The Deliverable concludes by presenting the planned Advocacy Workshops, targeting researchers and research organizations, libraries and infrastructure providers, as well as publishers and publication platforms, and by outlining advocacy materials the SIG has developed and will develop in the following months.

B. Definition of Open Science and Open Access

The OPERAS Advocacy SIG follows the OPERAS definitions of Open Science and Open Access³, where Open Science⁴ is defined as:

- Transparency in experimental methodology, observation, and collection of data
- Public availability and reusability of scientific data
- Public accessibility and transparency of scientific communication
- Using web-based tools to facilitate scientific collaboration

and Open Access⁵ is defined as:

- Free access to scientific publications with reuse allowed by the license attached to the publication.

We acknowledge that Open Science is more a process, attitude and approach, rather than a final goal.

C. Definition of Advocacy

The term “advocacy” is often used to describe an activity or process of “supporting a cause or proposal” (see Merriam Webster dictionary) and especially gaining “public support” (see Cambridge Dictionary) for this activity or idea. The activity can be carried out either by an individual or group. Organizations describing their advocacy activities most commonly use the term to show how they create central positions and use them to influence positions of political, public or economic institutions, e.g. the bodies of the European Union. This process often takes place by including a broader public community, both from within the organizations and from without. The advocacy process often works in both directions: organizations include public opinion in their creation of central positions but, at the same time, strive to influence public opinion.

The definitions of “lobbying” are much clearer than those for “advocacy”. The term is usually used to describe “activities aimed at influencing public officials and especially members of a legislative body on legislation” (see Merriam Webster dictionary). It is thus a form of advocacy that concentrates on approaching legislators directly.

The scope of the OPERAS Advocacy SIG encompasses all types of directed activities supporting its vision and mission and which are in line with its code of conduct.⁶ OPERAS’

³ see: OPERAS Rules of Participation:

https://operas.hypotheses.org/files/2020/02/OPERAS_Rules_of_Participation.pdf.

⁴ see: Dan Gezelter (2009-07-28), “What, Exactly, Is Open Science? | The Open Science Project”, accessed 30 December 2019, <http://openscience.org/what-exactly-is-open-science/>; OECD (2015-10-15), “Making Open Science a Reality”, OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, No. 25, OECD Publishing, Paris, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5jrs2f963zs1-en>.

⁵ see: Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002), “Read the Budapest Open Access Initiative”,

<https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>.

⁶ OPERAS Code of Conduct: <https://www.operas.unito.it/about/governance-schema/how-we-work-together/>.

vision is to make Open Science a reality for research in the SSH and achieve a scholarly communication system where knowledge produced in the social sciences and the humanities benefits researchers, academics, students and more generally the whole society across Europe and worldwide, without barriers. OPERAS' mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH. A special focus should be on gaining support from all stakeholders and target audiences as described below, as well as from a broader public. The Advocacy SIG, together with the OPERAS Coordination Team, strives to coordinate community central positions for the OPERAS RI and to ensure that the broader OPERAS community is involved in this process. The OPERAS SIG has a strong focus on empowering communities to influence decision-making processes.

D. Stakeholders and target audiences

The Advocacy SIG draws on the results of the Deliverable “Landscape study on scholarly needs and stakeholders in social sciences and humanities” (T2.3) of the OPERAS-P project for a definition of its main stakeholders and target audiences. The Deliverable defines the main categories of stakeholders in SSH scholarly communication as:

- service providers (publishers, dissemination platforms, repositories and other digital tools and services providers)
- policy makers
- e-Infrastructures and research infrastructures
- funders
- academic and research Institutions

Service providers, who enable and facilitate the creation, circulation and discovery of SSH scholarly content, usually have a national or regional reach. Thus, their networking and cooperation could contribute to greater efficiency, visibility, standardization and interoperability. Many business models that publishers rely on are still in the stage of formation and publishers often have a mixed business model, enabling them to cover costs from several sources of income. Service providers, including publishers, are an important target group of the Advocacy SIG not only because they make up the largest part of OPERAS members yet but also because their diversity and stronghold in the different communities makes it the more important to involve them in coordinating community central positions for the OPERAS Research Infrastructure.

Policy makers, both on a national and the EU level, do have Open Access and/or Open Science policies. The Advocacy SIG seeks to mainly target those policy makers who do not yet have strong policies and provide support, also in light of accommodating the specifics of SSH scholarly communication.

The national nodes of many research infrastructures relevant for the SSH disciplines (CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH, ESS, SHARE) are already well connected with OPERAS members. The Advocacy SIG seeks to ensure that the broader OPERAS community is

involved and to work closely with existing research infrastructures. Similarly, e-infrastructures under the umbrella of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and SSHOC, will be included in these efforts.

The Advocacy SIG recognizes that SSH research funding comes from various sources, i.e. from public and private funding, and international, national, regional or even local funding. Open Access policy adoption among private funders in particular could have a strong positive effect.

The uptake of Open Access mandates or policies among scholarly institutions is high in some countries and low in others. Scholarly institutions are thus a primary target group of the Advocacy SIG's activities to include them in coordinating community central positions for the OPERAS Research Infrastructure.⁷

II. Guide for addressing researchers' needs related to Open Access publishing

A. Methodology

The approach of the White Paper published by the Advocacy SIG in July 2018 was not to target researchers directly but rather guide other stakeholders to answer researchers' concerns. This chapter is a continuation and update of this White Paper and this approach and does therefore only target researchers indirectly. We have started gathering updates on how the situation has evolved since then. The results, a guide to all relevant stakeholders with concrete ideas on actions and projects, can thus be used by the OPERAS community, e.g. the OPERAS national nodes.

We have formulated questions to use in a survey on each of the topics that the White Paper has addressed. The questions are particularly targeted at those areas where we need more information or where we expect the situation to have changed and have been carefully selected to avoid receiving the same information we already have. The survey is meant to be very short with only four questions in total to ensure a wide participation. We do encourage participants to answer as detailed as possible. All questions will therefore be in an open format.

The survey will first be distributed among OPERAS partners. The answers will then be used to adapt the survey, if necessary, and distribute it among a broader group of people to widen the scope. Dissemination of the survey will be targeted at the relevant stakeholders (see chapter "I.D. Stakeholders and target audiences").

⁷ This chapter explicitly draws on the results of the Deliverable "Landscape study on scholarly needs and stakeholders in social sciences and humanities" (T2.3).

B. Survey questionnaire

The following four questions have been selected to be distributed among relevant stakeholders:

1. What can publishers and publication platforms do to help researchers who have difficulties covering the publishing charges?
2. How can publishers address researchers' concerns with academic reputation and/or the quality of the publication venue when publishing Open Access? If you are representing a publisher or a publication platform, what efforts are you making to support good peer review practices?
3. What informational resources and training would you like OPERAS to provide to help you or a publisher, publication platform, research organization or university to improve?
4. How is your institution making the administration process easier for APC-payments to Open Access publishers that fall outside of read-and-publish/pay-as-you-publish/offsetting agreements? Do you have any ideas on how the administration process could be improved?

C. Possible outcomes

We expect a turnout of approx. 100 answers to the survey. It will be distributed on the OPERAS social media channels and the OPERAS national nodes will be asked to share it with their national networks.

Question 1: What can publishers and publication platforms do to help researchers who have difficulties covering the publishing charges?

Possible outcomes: Publishers might have established or plan to establish a waiver scheme. They might also help authors in finding funding or help them by establishing and participating in programs to cover publishing costs, e.g. crowdfunding initiatives.

Question 2: How can publishers address researchers' concerns with academic reputation and/or the quality of the publication venue when publishing Open Access? If you are representing a publisher or a publication platform, what efforts are you making to support good peer review practices?

Possible outcomes: Publishers and publication platforms should make the publishing process as transparent as possible by providing full information about the editorial team, publishing reviewer guidelines, and describing the publisher's, journal's or platform's governance model and financing. In addition, the publishing venues might provide support for (or ensure) good peer review practices, e.g. trying to bet all their journals to COPE (<https://publicationethics.org/>) standards. Publishers and publication platforms might improve the quality of the publishing process and services by striving to reach a standard, e.g. by developing to get indexed in "whitelist" databases such as DOAJ, having authors complete Journal Score Cards in QOAM, or becoming Plan S-compliant.

Question 3: What informational resources and training would you like OPERAS to provide to help you or a publisher, publication platform, research organization or university to improve?

Possible outcomes: Researchers and publishers might be interested in a certification for the peer-review process, such as DOAB (OPERAS Certification Service). Moreover, universities could integrate Open Science education into graduate curricula and sign and implement DORA. Answers might show that it is necessary to provide more resources to and professionalize Open Access publishing services, e.g. not outsourcing but developing the skills in-house. It would be interesting to see how OPERAS can help here.

Question 4: How is your institution making the administration process easier for APC-payments to Open Access publishers that fall outside of read-and-publish/pay-as-you-publish/offsetting agreements? Do you have any ideas on how the administration process could be improved?

Possible outcomes: We have not included APC-related administrative hurdles in the previously published White Paper. However, we have stated that it is important that research organizations do not forget pure Open Access publishers. With the read-and-publish agreements, this is all the more important.

III. Advocacy for the SSH

A. Panel discussion

The Advocacy SIG envisions to develop a strategy on how to advocate for the SSH disciplines, particularly targeting funders and policy-makers, both at national and at European level. We have therefore organized a panel discussion at the annual OPERAS conference to draw conclusions from professional experiences of invited panelists.

We prepared a [list](#), based on research conducted by IBL PAN, of activists and experts from different institutions, think tanks, NGOs, Open Access initiatives, who are dealing professionally with advocacy for the SSH. We then selected eleven individuals and directly invited them to fill out the [submission form](#). The results of the received proposals are presented in the following chapter. We have invited five to present their case studies at the OPERAS conference.

Panel title: How to advocate for social sciences and humanities

Date: Monday, 2 November 2020, 9:30 am - 11:00 am, CET

Moderator: Sally Chambers, Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities

Chairs: Elisabeth Ernst, Mateusz Franczak

Panelists: Marc Vanholsbeeck, Alíz Horváth, Jane Ohlmeyer, Jack Spaapen, Nina Kancewicz-Hoffman

The goal of this panel is to develop a strategy on how to advocate for the SSH disciplines and to target funders and policy makers, both at national and at European level. Conclusions will be based on the professional experience of the panelists. The exchange of both advocacy experiences and as examples of actual best practices, challenges, or obstacles will help us in finding a common ground to operate on the EU level while taking into account local specificities. This panel will include brief presentations on how to advocate for the SSH disciplines in European countries by working with funders, policy makers, researchers and other stakeholders. The session will be based on actual examples of such activities. Presentations will be followed by a moderated Q&A.

Information obtained from the presentations and discussion during the conference will supply the documentation for OPERAS to present to community and policy makers. Best practices featured in case studies can be later shared with new members as a basis to operate on EU and national level. Exchanging experiences connected to advocacy, showing examples of best practices and challenges or obstacles related to local specifics during the panel will provide input for the Advocacy SIG work, but may also attract new organizations to join OPERAS and become active within the community.

B. First results: panelists' contributions

a. Integrating the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences in Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Research: lessons from the SHAPE-ID project

The following abstract was submitted by Jane Ohlmeyer, Professor, Trinity College Dublin, College Green, Dublin, Ireland.

Aim. SHAPE-ID is a Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action that aims to improve pathways for integrating Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences (AHSS) disciplines into inter- and transdisciplinary research in Europe.

Gaps and challenges. Despite broad rhetorical support for this aim for many years at policy level, practical supports have been limited and progress has been modest. SHAPE-ID aims to establish a solid evidence base to underpin a toolkit designed to guide policymakers, funders, research performing institutions and researchers towards better AHSS integration pathways.

Methods. SHAPE-ID has conducted an extensive review (qualitative and quantitative) of both academic and policy literatures, a qualitative survey and a series of stakeholder workshops on different challenges to learn more about what obstructs and enables inter- and transdisciplinary research with AHSS integration.

Results and Discussion. SHAPE-ID's results to date have confirmed recommendations made in previous reports but not adopted by policymakers and funders, and identified a gap in understanding across the academic and policy communities when it comes to understanding inter- and transdisciplinary research and confirmed an urgent need to build

common ground between researchers and policymakers. The project produced a policy brief distilling the results of the literature reviews and survey, making the following key recommendations:

- a) Involve experts in inter- and transdisciplinarity and from across the spectrum of AHSS disciplines in defining, designing and evaluating inter- and transdisciplinary research funding calls.
- b) Develop funding programmes that acknowledge the need to dedicate resources to the collaborative dimensions of inter and transdisciplinary research and build mutual understanding within projects, allowing time and money for such dimensions.
- c) Support and incentivise universities to de-risk inter- and transdisciplinary research careers, integrate inter- and transdisciplinarity into education and training of researchers at all levels (undergraduate, graduate and postdoctoral), and offer training for faculty in managing inter- and transdisciplinary research projects, designing and reviewing proposals for funding and evaluating the impact of inter- and transdisciplinarity.
- d) Support a toolkit of inter- and transdisciplinary research methods, materials and best practice for AHSS integration to enable capacity building and better sharing of knowledge between communities.

SHAPE-ID continues its advocacy for AHSS integration through submissions to invited consultations such as the Horizon Europe public consultation and the International Science Council Global Call for Priorities for Science, and works to engage more and more stakeholders in these discussions through its webinars and outreach to funders and policymakers.

Conclusion. Much more still needs to be done to ensure the AHSS are meaningfully integrated into interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research funding programmes as a matter of course. AHSS communities need to learn to forge better relationships with policymakers and work to persuade the wider world why these disciplines need to be at the heart of how we address the major challenges we face as a society. It is hoped that the SHAPE-ID results and toolkit will be an enabling and impactful contribution to these ongoing efforts.

References.

Vienni Baptista, B., Lyall, C., Ohlmeyer, J., Spaapen, J., Wallace, D. & Pohl, C. (2020). Improving pathways to interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research for the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences: first lessons from the SHAPE-ID project – Policy Brief. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3824953

b. Strengthening the role of AHSS in science and society

The following abstract was submitted by Jack Spaapen, Dr., independent expert on research and innovation policy and retired senior policy advisor at the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences.

Most if not all scientific fields that regard human behaviour as a rule work on the interface that connects the world of scientific research and the world of society and policy. These worlds have become more and more entangled, especially in the last three decades, but there is still a lack of mutual understanding on what drives these two worlds. That makes the interaction between the two always a challenge, but this seems to be more so for Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences (AHSS) than for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields, at least this is my experience from talking to policy makers and funders.

There are two areas that I would like to talk about in this respect, the one regards evaluation: what are the consequences for the assessment of AHSS proposals in funding processes. The other is the role of AHSS in multi, inter- and transdisciplinary research.

I will illustrate these two areas respectively with a Dutch example of an evaluation protocol that put the narrative central in the evaluation process (www.qrih.nl), and with the results of a European survey on inter- and transdisciplinarity (www.shapeid.eu).

c. Timeless Relevance: How Humanista: The Podcast Promotes the Humanities Globally

The following abstract was submitted by Aliz Horvath, PhD, Concept creator and host of Humanista: The Podcast (humanistathepodcast.com); Assistant Professor in East Asian History and Digital Humanities, Eötvös Loránd University East Asian Institute.

Overview. “Created by humanists about the humanities to explore what we can learn about the world through humanistic lens and what the role of the humanities is in the 21st century” says the mission statement of Humanista: The Podcast, a novel and experimental project aiming to promote the multifaceted diversity and timeless value of the humanities. Conceived in Tokyo, launched in Chicago, and recorded worldwide (both in person and remotely), this collaborative and pro-bono series features accessible, but also thought-provoking, conversations with humanists of varying nationalities, interests, and backgrounds in multiple languages using contemporary digital media platforms. Focusing on the conceptual and practical aspects of the project and my visions for its future, I explore how Humanista strives to showcase and advocate for the relevance of humanistic fields by shedding fresh light on their seemingly familiar and surprisingly non-standard manifestations in society.

Detailed discussion. Podcasting as a genre constitutes an emerging platform for research communication and knowledge dissemination in the humanities and humanistic social sciences. Its growing significance and use can be witnessed, for example, in its inclusion in recent conference programs, such as the Annual Meeting of the American

Historical Association in 2020 (American Historical Association, 2020) and its appearance as a novel pedagogical tool in higher education (McLoughlin, Lee & Chan, 2006; Mitchell, 2020). The broad range of themes covered by humanities-related podcasts seems to emulate the thematic diversity of podcasts in general, but a recurring tendency among them can still be witnessed in the form of relatively narrow topics and approaches or an institutional connection. For instance, Carrie Jenkins' Labels of Love (with one complete season) (Jenkins, C., 2017-2019) illustrates how a niche issue can be grasped effectively in a collaborative and independent podcast setting, whereas the New Books Network consortium (New Books Network, 2010) introduces a variety of topics through interviews with the authors of recently published scholarly books.

My contribution, Humanista, can be situated in between these major types of podcasts because it explores the humanities as a phenomenon with a broad thematic focus, while maintaining an independent and relatively personal tone to further "humanize" the topics at hand. Humanista is not area-specific and aims to target a broad audience with an interest and openness to explore, together with the participants of each session, the sometimes overlooked value that humanistic approaches bring to diverse fields. The podcast helps connect scholars by shedding light on differing traditions and characteristics of humanistic inquiry across continents, but in the meantime, it also introduces young listeners a variety of possible career paths with a humanistic background, including libraries, translation, digital media, etc. Moreover, in a broader sense, the podcast explores how the humanities might help us understand complex social issues, such as migration, development, and belonging.

If one embarks on the journey of launching a podcast, a variety of factors need to be considered from securing proper equipment to creating the most suitable online platform and schedule for the program. However, what I have found to be the most challenging aspect of my project is the question of effective promotion. This still constitutes an ongoing issue, but in the following, I will briefly explain the practical strategy I have utilized so far.

In terms of outreach, I have found my guests to be cooperative in the dissemination of the respective episodes of the series. I started the podcast by initially inviting individuals from my relatively closer professional environment who were already familiar with me and my work. This technique not only resulted in lively conversations and plenty of revelatory novelties, but also contributed to the creation of a solid basis as a sort of reference, facilitating a more effective future outreach to further potential participants who I am not yet acquainted with.

Another important point to note here is the role and significance of care from the side of all parties involved in the podcast. While I manage and oversee the entire production process and social media promotion of the podcast on my own as a pro-bono engagement, the series would not be nearly as successful without the reciprocated care shown by the guests as well – even without monetary remuneration. Their enthusiasm, which itself proves the need for such a new media platform, has translated to contributions to the promotion of the episodes in their network and social media channels as well, taking the name of the podcast to farther communities than initially expected.

My visions for the future of the podcast are two-fold: on the one hand, I aim to consistently maintain the accessible, but thought-provoking, tone and goal of the series by placing themes into the spotlight that have largely been underrepresented in the media. On the other hand, I also intend to further expand the coverage of the podcast through novel, innovative, and experimental collaborations. This could take the form of, for example, 1) conversations featuring not only individuals, but also organizations and communities working towards the promotion of humanities; 2) collaborations with scholars who are also exploring new media platforms (such as Youtube) to reach the contemporary information consumer; as well as 3) “untraditional humanists”, that is people with a humanistic background currently working in fields not necessarily directly associated with the humanities or vice versa. Such an approach will ideally help grasp and articulate the multilayered role and relevance of the humanities even more effectively while enhancing its visibility in society.

Keywords: podcast, humanities, diversity, new media, advocacy

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134th Annual Meeting of the American Historical Association Conference Program. (2020) Podcasting History. Retrieved from <https://aha.confex.com/aha/2020/webprogram/Session19562.html>

d. The value of the social sciences to the key dilemmas Europe faces

The following abstract was submitted by Nina Kancewicz-Hoffman, Dr., Institute of Literary Research, Polish Academy of Sciences (IBL PAN).

The Standing Committee for Social Sciences (SCSS) of the European Science Foundation (ESF) supported diverse research activities but also strategic activities in research policy domain⁸. The research initiatives funded by SCSS had an European scope in terms of topics and researchers involved, thus potentially were directly relevant for European policies. Members of the Committee were aware however that these activities and their results are not sufficiently known among policy makers. The Committee undertook therefore a number of activities promoting the value and impact of social sciences for the society targeting European policy makers.

In 2012 SCSS organised in the European Parliament (EP) in Brussels a conference ‘The Science of Innovation’⁹ and in 2015 two events: ‘Demographic Change in Europe’¹⁰ and ‘Inequalities in Europe’¹¹.

The aim was two-fold: on one hand to prove to the ESF funders (research funding and research performing organisations from 30 European countries) that activities they are funding are visible to and appreciated by European policy makers, mainly by the European Commission and the European Parliament; on the other hand to directly impact European policies in areas where SCSS-funded projects made a significant contribution.

ESF was already collaborating with Science and Technology Options Assessment (STOA) Panel of the EP and the idea of the event, and subsequently the selection of the topic and the best way to ensure participation of the European policy makers were agreed with STOA. The Programme Committee of the conference included social scientists representing SCSS and MEPs – members of the STOA Panel. Taking into consideration new research on innovation and the role of innovation in European polices the topic selected was The Science of Innovation.

A full day conference took place in a large conference room of the EP in Brussel¹². The invitation to the conference was addressed to MEPs and their staff, the European Commission staff but also to academics and practitioners (business organisations, national governments and politicians, think tanks etc.) all over Europe. The agenda was organised in three sessions; each session consisted of an introduction by a MEP – STOA Panel member followed by presentations of leading academics in the subject. The conference

⁸ <http://archives.esf.org/hosting-experts/scientific-review-groups/social-sciences-soc.html>.

⁹ <http://archives.esf.org/hosting-experts/scientific-review-groups/social-sciences-soc/activities/strategic-activities/the-science-of-innovation.html>.

¹⁰ <http://archives.esf.org/hosting-experts/scientific-review-groups/social-sciences-soc/activities/strategic-activities/evening-debate-on-demographic-change-in-europe.html>.

¹¹ <http://archives.esf.org/hosting-experts/scientific-review-groups/social-sciences-soc/activities/strategic-activities/evening-debate-on-inequalities-in-europe.html>.

¹² <http://archives.esf.org/hosting-experts/scientific-review-groups/social-sciences-soc/activities/strategic-activities/the-science-of-innovation.html>.

was concluded by a panel discussion including MEPs, speakers and a Commission representative and was followed by a reception. This format was aimed at stimulating an exchange of opinions and networking between the MEPs and the Commission staff and speakers and the participants.

The detailed advice from STOA was taken into consideration regarding the list of speakers who potentially could attract policy makers and the technicalities of the organisation. On one hand information on the event was widely disseminated and on the other targeted invitations were sent out. Although a maximum number of participants was registered (about 90 including speakers and organisers) actual participation of MEPs was lower than expected. The majority of participants were academics from all over Europe and their evaluation of the event was very positive. Following the conference SCSS together with STOA published and disseminated a policy brief¹³ summarising the conference for policy makers and practitioners. However the dialog between research and policy was not established and there were no follow-up contacts with the Commission or the Parliament.

While the results were not fully satisfactory in the opinion of SCSS members, the conclusion was that a long term approach is necessary to introduce evidence-informed policy-making to the Parliament and the Commission. Following an analysis of 2012 conference two challenges were identified: to better adapt events to the busy schedule of MEPs, and to create a more friendly and attractive environment for discussions between researchers-speakers and policy makers. A new format was proposed: a series of short evening events with a limited number of participants, mainly MEPs and their staff and the Commission staff, enabling more direct contacts between the participants and the speakers. SCSS was joined by ALLEA to strengthen the representation of European research. The collaboration with STOA (which in the meantime became a part of the European Parliamentary Research Services - EPRS) was continued.

Two topics were selected as relevant: 'Demographic Change in Europe' and 'Inequalities in Europe' based on a significant volume of new research on both topics and the fact that the topics were among strategic priorities of the European Commission for the Horizon 2020 Work Programmes under discussion.

The venue for 2015 events named 'Evening Debates' was a library room in the EP in Brussels. Their scheduling (including the day of the week and evening hours) was strictly adapted to MEPs schedule and the events were promoted among target audience.

The first event was moderated by a MEP - Vice-Chair of the EP Committee on Employment and Social Affairs and featured three speakers from the academia but with experience in policy advice. The assumption was that via the Vice-Chair the participation of other members of the EP Committee will be encouraged. In the next event high level EP staff was invited as speakers accompanied by a larger panel of academic experts, also with very strong policy advice experience. Both events were followed by a working dinner

¹³

http://archives.esf.org/index.php?eID=tx_nawsecuredl&u=0&g=0&t=1603748478&hash=7961e0c6102c778205f5d6772723f2bd6abf5c1b&file=/fileadmin/be_user/research_areas/social_sciences/documents/SCSS/Innovation_Conference/Science_Innovation.pdf

for participating policy makers and speakers. The participation of the main target group, that is MEPs, was still rather limited.

Conclusions:

- The aim of SCSS – to promote social sciences results for policy making – is extremely difficult to achieve and requires a long-term approach.
- It is crucial to have good partners in the academia and on the policy side.
- Policy makers are overwhelmed with invitations and meetings. They have to be convinced that proposed meetings will be uniquely useful and informative. Maybe the events were too traditional, too academic, and a more innovative format should be proposed.
- It should be noted however that due to the fact that ESF SCSS was dissolved in 2015 only short term impact could be recorded. Obviously the Commission policies regarding innovation have changed since 2012. However the change cannot be attributed solely to the conference, the new thinking about innovation was getting more and more widespread and finally made its way to the policy.

e. Covid-19 as a plea for more Open Science also in the Social Sciences and the Humanities

The following abstract was submitted by Marc Vanholsbeeck, PhD, Ministry of Wallonia-Brussels Federation.

Aim: My presentation is inspired on the one hand by my recent experience of trying to register the research done on Covid-19, in health sciences, STEM as well as in SSH, in the universities of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation, notably in the perspective of a Belgian participation to the European Covid-19 Data Portal (<https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>). On the other hand, it will reflect the work which is currently being done within the ERAC (European Research Area Committee) Standing Working Group on Open Science and Innovation (SWG OSI) about Open Science and the Covid-19 crisis, which should lead to the publication of an opinion paper in the coming weeks. My communication is not in any way to be considered though as a presentation of the OSI report itself which has still to be finalized and validated by the OSI group.

The aim of the presentation is threefold. First I will contextualize the SSH contribution to an Open Science approach towards the pandemic within the broader context of the impact of the Covid-19 crisis on Open Science, at the level of scholarly communication, policy making and science communication. Second, I will present the opportunities and challenges that the pandemic has brought to light for Open Science in general, and more specifically for the fostering of the openness paradigm within the SSH. Third, I will discuss some ways of improving the potential of Open Science, and Open Science in the SSH disciplines in particular, in the fight against Covid-19.

Gaps and challenges: Bibliometricians have shown that the number of studies published during the outbreak of Covid-19 has exceeded by far the scientific production linked to

previous pandemics (Aristovnik et al., 2020). Furthermore a substantial amount of articles have been published ahead-of-print with submission-to-publication reduced around 10 times on average (Homolak et al., 2020). Publishers have also granted temporary or partial open access to Covid-19 articles while researchers have massively used preprints to share early results. Among other remarkable initiatives that relate to Open Research Data, the European Covid-19 Data Portal aims at facilitating data sharing and analysis, in order to accelerate coronavirus research. At policy level, there have been calls from national rectors' conferences and national consortia as well as governments to publishers to open access to Covid-19 related literature. General media have raised the topic of scholarly communication and Open Science like never before.

In this unprecedented context, SWG OSI intends to fill a gap in terms of evidence based policy recommendations relating to Open Science and the pandemic. In particular we deemed it useful to raise the awareness of EU and national policy makers about the role of SSH research in the fight against the pandemic, and the opportunities and challenges that relate to the fostering of the openness paradigm in these disciplines.

One particular challenge while trying to register Covid-19 related research at national level consisted in getting relevant and complete information about the existence of Covid related datasets, as well as the accessibility and/or the level of „FAIRification“ thereof. While researchers and research institutions are generally keen to provide information about their Covid-19 related research projects, they are – notably but not only in the SSH – not yet used to communicate about the related datasets.

Methods (Background): The SWG OSI opinion paper will be based on members' experience in regard to Covid-19 and Open Science management, desk research and a dedicated SWG OSI register of Open Science and Open Innovation related initiatives in the context of the pandemic. This register has been completed in Spring and Summer 2020 by OSI members as well as by external stakeholders and was conceived as complementary to the monitoring done at EU level by the Governing Board of the EOSC in the perspective of the Covid-19 Portal (<http://www.covid19dataportal.org/>).

SWG OSI – which I currently chair - aims at advising the ERAC, the Commission as well as the Member States and Associated Countries on the development and implementation of policies and initiatives to enhance the access to scientific information and the circulation and use of knowledge for research and innovation, for the benefit of scientists, research institutions, education, businesses, citizens and society at large. OSI members are European public servants in charge of Open Science policies in their country.

Results and Discussion (Discussion): I will discuss some ways of improving the potential of Open Science, and Open Science in the SSH disciplines in particular, in the fight against Covid-19.

Conclusion: Thanks to the rapid flow of information from experimental and clinical research in the health sciences, open science has enabled the medical management of the pandemic to progress at a fast pace. Facing the pandemic also requests the development of interdisciplinary approaches that include the contribution from SSH

researchers as well, for providing solutions to the social, economic, psychological and communicational challenges linked to the Covid-19.

It is therefore imperative, in the general interest, to learn the lessons of the current crisis and to make arrangements for a free flow of information from public research of any kind. Since SSH research is an integral part to any sustainable solution to the complex challenges caused by the pandemic, an equal attention should be dedicated to the fostering of the openness paradigm in all disciplines.

Key words: Open Science, Covid-19, SSH, Open Research Data, Science Communication

References:

Aristovnik, A., Ravšelj, D., & Umek, L. (2020). A Bibliometric Analysis of COVID-19 across Science and Social Science Research Landscape. Preprints, 2020060299 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202006.0299.v4).

Homolak, J., Kodvanj, I., & Virag, D. (2020). Preliminary analysis of COVID-19 academic information patterns: a call for open science in the times of closed borders. *Scientometrics*, 1-15.

IV. National channels for Open Access publishing

The Advocacy SIG plans on working on national channels to inform policy-makers and advocate the SIG’s topics to them. This will be achieved in cooperation with the OPERAS national nodes and T3.3 Support to National Nodes of the project OPERAS-P. Questions, among others, to be discussed are:

- Do we need to promote and advocate for OPERAS activities at country levels?
- Do we need to raise more awareness about the benefits of joining OPERAS nationally?
- Do we need OPERAS websites in each country?
- Do we need more coverage of OPERAS’ activities in local social networks?
- Do we need SSH mailing lists at country levels?
- How to reach SSH researchers in each country?
- Could we develop some guidelines on how to set-up communication channels in different countries?
- Do we need a “starter set” with basic information that is customized to policy-makers in each country?

The results of this topic will be presented in the final OPERAS Advocacy White Paper.

V. Advocacy Workshops

A. Researchers and research organizations

Researchers not actively seeking information about Open Access and scholars who are not actively informed by their institutions might be concerned about publishing Open Access due to lack of information. Questions such as “Why is Open Access necessary and what do I gain?”, “What happens to my rights as an author?”, and “Why was I not told about this discount before I paid the full APC from my project fund?” might come up.

The OPERAS SIG therefore organizes a workshop on advocacy for Open Access in the SSH, particularly targeting researchers, as a pre-conference workshop of the [15th Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing](#) to take place 18/19 November 2020.

Workshop title: How to fill the information gap: Open Access for the social sciences and humanities

Date: Tuesday, 17 November 2020

Moderators: Elisabeth Ernst (Max Weber Stiftung), Judith Schulte (Max Weber Stiftung)

This workshop is directed at representatives of research organizations and universities (e.g. Open Access offices, project coordinators, and interested researchers) on the topic of helping researchers finding answers to these questions and advocating for Open Access in the humanities and social sciences. The workshop seeks to discuss aspects that have been identified by participants before the workshop as most pressing to discuss. Participants are therefore invited to fill in a short survey by 9 November 2020. The results of the survey will not only be discussed at the workshop but they can also be further used by the OPERAS community, particularly the OPERAS national nodes.

The questions of the survey are:

1. Please rank the most common issues that researchers may encounter due to not actively seeking or receiving information about Open Access. (1 = most common issue, 5 or lower = least common issue)
 - a. Unclear rationale behind Open Access. Many researchers do not realise that access is provided by their institutions in exchange for highly priced subscription fees and that their peers at lesser funded institutions, as well as individuals outside of academia only have restricted access to scholarly literature. Consequently, for some researchers (early career researchers as well as established scholars), the motivations behind Open Access may seem unclear.
 - b. Lacking understanding of author rights. Due to a lack of information, especially concerning intellectual property rights (e.g., the distinction between copyright and licence) and the possibility to uniquely identify their publications (e.g., Crossref DOIs), researchers may be afraid to lose the rights to or control over their work when publishing Open Access.

- c. Lacking understanding of the chances and advantages of Open Access publishing (e.g. better findability, better reuse of material, etc.).
 - d. Funders do not communicate their Open Access requirements clearly.
 - e. It is untransparent which, or if, APC discounts have been negotiated by the research organization/university.
 - f. Missing some overview over Open Access publishing possibilities in the different disciplines.
 - g. Fear of losing reputation.
 - h. Other. Please specify.
2. What is your research organization, university, or Open Access office doing to counteract these issues? Please tick as relevant and specify.
 - a. Information and support channels.
 - b. Targeted advocacy to funders to clearly state their Open Access requirements
 - c. Research and advocacy measures to show that Open Access and Open Science have become one of the leading ways of conducting scientific research and that the landscape is evolving quickly, increasing the possibilities of scientific research, not limiting them.
 - d. Other. Please specify.
 3. Please enter any ideas on concrete actions that could be taken to tackle the issue of lacking information on Open Access.
 4. What, in your opinion, is the single greatest benefit of Open Access?

B. Libraries and infrastructure providers

This workshop, organized by UniTo (Italy), will take place in Spring 2021.

C. Publishers and publication platforms

This workshop, organized by Coimbra (Portugal), will take place in Spring 2021. Coimbra is currently in discussion with the Portuguese Association of Higher Education Press and has suggested collaborating in organizing the event. The suggestion was well received and the probable date of the workshop would be 22 April 2021. More details are going to be discussed in November 2020.

VI. Advocacy Materials

The OPERAS Advocacy SIG will work and has worked on the following topics to produce advocacy material for the community to use. The OPERAS Executive Assembly members will be asked to translate the statements in their respective languages. The following statements will be adapted and brought to a common format to use as advocacy materials.

A. About OPERAS

OPERAS is the distributed Research Infrastructure to enable Open Science and upgrade scholarly communication practices in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). SSH disciplines require specific approaches to transition to both digital practices and open science, as it is evidenced in numerous studies and reports: they produce specific research outputs (books, critical editions), work in multiple different languages, and embed interpretation in their epistemic models. The vision of OPERAS is to make open science a reality for research in the SSH and achieve a scholarly communication system where knowledge produced in the SSH benefits researchers, academics, students and, more generally to address societal challenges and support society reach the sustainable development goals.

OPERAS is not building a single facility, but pools the resources to let all SSH stakeholders perform more efficiently their activities and maximize the societal impact of their work, in an inter- and transdisciplinary, mission-driven approach. To achieve a more efficient, fair, inclusive and sustainable ecosystem OPERAS puts an emphasis on digital technologies, digital methods and standard adoption to increase openness of both data and publications. OPERAS supports new ways of discovering, reusing, creating, crosslinking, sharing, annotating and mixing data across a variety of languages, topics, disciplines, scientific communities to open new perspectives on both traditional research topics and cutting edge research topics.

B. One-pagers of the OPERAS White Papers

The OPERAS White Papers will be ready by June 2021. The OPERAS SIG has prepared documents for each SIG White Paper to create advocacy statements for each of them once they are ready: [Advocacy](#), [Common Standards](#), [Multilingualism](#), [Open Access Business Models](#), [Platforms and Services](#), [Tools Research and Development](#).

C. OPERAS statements

The OPERAS SIG has identified the following five areas for which an advocacy statement is most pressing: Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism, Bibliodiversity, FAIR initiative (CO-OPERAS), open licensing, and principles and guidelines for establishing national Open Access publishing infrastructures. The SIG will continue identifying topics for statements that are necessary and produce these in the following months.

D. OPERAS Services

The Advocacy SIG, in cooperation with OPERAS' Technical Officer and the Communication Officers for the respective projects, have produced Advocacy Statements on each of the following services. The statements will be adopted in the course of the next months to clearly focus on the respective target groups.

a. *Discovery Service*

The Discovery Service is currently under development thanks to the Horizon 2020 EU [TRIPLE project](#). It is operated by [Huma-Num](#) and will provide European Researchers a single point to discover SSH open scholarly resources such as data, publications, and other researchers and projects which are currently scattered across local repositories. The Discovery Service allows for the discovery of resources in different languages from a variety of sources across multiple countries. The service will be based on the existing French ISIDORE platform provided by Huma-Num, with many more extra languages to be discovered, and additional innovative services directly plugged-in the platform such as annotation service, recommendation service, trust-building service, visualization service, etc.

The Discovery Service is currently under development. Its operation is planned for 2023.

b. *Certification Service*

The Certification Service has been developed thanks to the HIRMEOS project. It is operated by the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), which collects the variety of peer reviewing practices from hundreds of monograph publishing houses, categorizes them, and provides a single access point to the list of certified peer reviewed monographs available in Open Access in the world. DOAB is a digital directory of peer-reviewed Open Access books and Open Access book publishers. The primary aim of the service is to increase discoverability of Open Access books so that they can reach a broader audience. The Certification Service operates as a quality insurance service for the benefit of readers and the service providers working with them, such as the libraries. OPERAS is publishing its services to the EOSC, for a better reach to the researchers, and the Certification

Service was the first one to reach this stage on the Marketplace.¹⁴

Access to the service: <https://doabooks.org/>

Contact for the service: technical-support@operas-eu.org

c. Metrics Service

Within the Hirmeos project we created a standardized usage and alternative metrics service for open access monographs. This was designed on the assumption that authors, publishers, platforms need to have access to those data in a simple and transparent way. For open access content, the challenge is that the same content is disseminated on and cited from several platforms (institutional repository, international dissemination platforms, publishers website etc.) and that it is difficult for content creators to collect usage data from those different publication and dissemination venues. As a result the metrics service achieves a comprehensive and transparent mechanism to collect and aggregate usage metrics on monographs from third-party platforms, and provides a single access point through a common API. The service is composed of three parts: altmetrics and citations metrics database, a public API and a widget to display all metrics on the partners' websites, a dashboard intended for publishers to help them track and analyse the usage of their publications.

More information on the service: <https://metrics.operas-eu.org/>

d. Publication Service Portal (PSP)

Developed within the OPERAS-P project, the Publication Service Portal (PSP), ("Pathfinder"), will be operated jointly by the University of Torino and Lexis Compagnia Editoriale. The service will collect the publishing and scholarly communication services that OPERAS members offer, and provides descriptive information all accessible via this single access portal. The portal will be composed of two different parts: a catalog of services categorized and a wizard that walks researchers through a series of questions towards the different services that best fits their needs. With the use of a federated authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI), OPERAS members will be able to simply provide the information of their services in order to grow the catalog and provide new relevant services to the research community.

Access to the service: beta version will be available early 2022, final version early 2023

Contact for the service: technical-support@operas-eu.org

¹⁴ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/operas-certification-doab>.

e. *Entity-Fishing*

The Entity-Fishing service, previously known as NERD, identifies and disambiguates entities mentioned in text. The process includes a Named Entity Recogniser for identifying open entities in text (such as person, places, dates, etc.) based on Conditional Random Field modelling and a disambiguation of entities against Wikipedia and FreeBases entries, based on statistical measures and a Random Tree Forest regression. The identification and resolution of named-entities like person-name, location, etc. provides many practical applications, e.g. possibility to extract lists of people, to map different texts, to generate timelines and to provide an enhanced search. This is of great importance not only for research but also for the publishing process.

Access to the service: <https://github.com/kermitt2/entity-fishing>

f. *Research for Society*

The Research for Society Service is designed to be an interactive platform between SSH researchers and the society at large. Developing the practices of academic blogging, the hypotheses.org platform already offers to SSH researchers the ability to build an open conversation with socio-economic actors, more particularly regarding the societal challenges. Currently, Hypotheses.org allows for communication practices in support of a wide range of interactions with the society, from science popularization (<https://sms.hypotheses.org/>) to intensively collaborative projects (<https://places.hypotheses.org>). In its future stages of development, the service will provide, thanks to project funding, more support to intensive collaboration projects, with additional resources such as collaborative tools, funding opportunities, and a matchmaking service to foster and support the desire to collaborate on citizen science projects.

VII. Dissemination level

PU = Public

